

Cardiac T1-mapping using Open-MOLLI at 3T: a repeatability study

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INTRODUCTION:

Quantitative MR measurements suffer from several confounding factors that need to be controlled to increase confidence in the measurements and in their diagnostic capability [1]. Currently, myocardium T1 mapping suffers from variability due to implementation differences across systems, which impact the influence of other processes such as magnetization transfer. This could be addressed by using tools such as Pulseseq [2] that allow the same sequence to be applied across different systems [3,4]. The repeatability of the previously developed open-source myocardial T1 mapping (Open-MOLLI) sequence [5] was tested at 3.0T and compared to the MOLLI [6] sequence, continuing the preliminary study presented at the ISMRM 2023-24 Reproducibility Team challenge by including a larger cohort of 15 healthy subjects.

METHODS:

MOLLI comprises an inversion-recovery (IR) sequence with a balanced steady-state free precession imaging (bSSFP) readout for T1 mapping. Open-MOLLI uses the same IR strategy as MOLLI with the trigger scheme 5(3)3. It is publicly available at <https://github.com/asgaspar/OpenMOLLI>. This sequence was tested at 3.0T in the context of the ISMRM Reproducibility Challenge “Repeat it with me” in a different center from the original study at 1.5T [5]. This work expands on those preliminary results by including a larger cohort.

Open-MOLLI and MOLLI were acquired in 15 healthy subjects (34 ± 11 years) using a 3.0T Siemens PrismaFit Scanner with a 32-channel body coil, and the sequence was repeated in each session to study repeatability. The acquisition

was performed in three middle myocardial slices, and the mean myocardial T1 was estimated across slices.

MOLLI was acquired with field-of-view (FOV) of $354 \times 302 \text{ mm}^2$, with partial Fourier (PF) applied in both directions (acquired matrix 202×124 - PF of 86% in the phase direction and 79% in the readout direction). For Open-MOLLI, the FOV was $354 \times 327 \text{ mm}^2$. The initial (and shortest) inversion time (TI) was 171 ms for Open-MOLLI and 100 ms for MOLLI. The acquisition parameters are presented in Table 1.

Data were reconstructed offline using GRAPPA, and adaptive coil combination to obtain Phase Sensitive Inversion Recovery signals that were used for T1 estimation in Matlab. A 3-parameter model $\text{Signal}(A,B,T1^*)=A \cdot B \cdot \exp(-TI/T1^*)$ with correction of $T1 = (B/A-1)T1^*$ was used [1]. Manual segmentation of the myocardium was performed.

The accuracy of Open-MOLLI T1 estimates was evaluated by considering MOLLI T1 values as the reference in a Bland-Altman analysis. A paired, two-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test was performed to compare MOLLI and Open-MOLLI results, p-values below 0.05 were considered significant. The within-subject coefficient of variation (CVw) was estimated calculating the ratio of the within-subject standard deviation (SD) to its mean value. The repeatability coefficient (RC) is given in percentage from $RC (\%) = 2.77CVw$.

RESULTS:

MOLLI and Open-MOLLI sequences were acquired in 15 subjects, but one repetition of one subject was excluded from the repeatability analysis due to severe artifacts related to heart motion. Figure 1 shows the T1-weighted images obtained for the first TI obtained with MOLLI and Open-MOLLI for one representative subject; T1 maps for the same subject are also presented.

Mean myocardial T1 over all slices and included subjects was $T1^{\text{MOLLI}} = 1148 \pm 24 \text{ ms}$ vs $T1^{\text{Open-MOLLI}} = 1129 \pm 41 \text{ ms}$. The mean T1 difference between Open-MOLLI and MOLLI was -18 ms (p-value=0.06) with a confidence interval of [-89, 52] ms (see Figure 2A and 2B).

Regarding within session test-retest results, no statistical differences were found between repetitions for the T1 estimates obtained with either sequence (Figure 3); the mean T1 difference between scans for MOLLI and Open-MOLLI were $\Delta T1^{\text{MOLLI}} = -2.2 \text{ ms}$ (p-value=0.30) and $\Delta T1^{\text{Open-MOLLI}} = 4.8 \text{ ms}$ (p-value=0.11). The confidence interval (1.96 SD) of the mean difference for MOLLI was [-17, 13] ms, while for Open-MOLLI it was [-16, 24] ms. The RC within-subject was 0.48% for MOLLI and 0.71% for Open-MOLLI.

The repeatability of both sequences ($RC^{\text{MOLLI}}=0.48\%$; $RC^{\text{Open-MOLLI}}=0.71\%$) was similar to the previous cohort ($RC^{\text{MOLLI}}=0.37\%$; $RC^{\text{Open-MOLLI}}=0.54\%$) at 3.0T [5,7]. This was better than at 1.5T ($RC^{\text{MOLLI}}=3.0\%$; $RC^{\text{Open-MOLLI}}=4.4\%$) [5] possibly due to an improvement in signal-to-noise ratio at 3.0T.

DISCUSSION:

The current cohort showed a bias between Open-MOLLI and MOLLI of -18 ms, similar to the results of the smaller sample (N=5) presented at the Reproducibility Challenge at 3.0T ($\Delta T_1=-22$ ms). Further tests will be performed to evaluate the segmental distribution, but the current results show a comparable robustness for the Open-MOLLI and MOLLI method. Although further tests are needed to evaluate Open-MOLLI's clinical performance, these are promising results towards increasing accessibility to myocardial T1 mapping.

CONCLUSION:

This work shows that the repeatability of MOLLI and Open-MOLLI are similar at 3.0T in a larger cohort. With the implementation of Open-MOLLI in a different center, we show that this sequence can be easily applied in inter-scanner reproducibility studies.

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Images

Figure 1: T1-weighted images obtained with MOLLI and Open-MOLLI in a healthy subject, and respective T1 maps (in ms) for both sequences. The T1 maps obtained with Open-MOLLI have a similar visual quality and tissue values comparable to MOLLI.

Figure 2: Comparison between MOLLI and Open-MOLLI over 15 subjects: (A) Correlation between MOLLI and Open-MOLLI; (B) Bland-Altman analysis comparing T1 values obtained with Open-MOLLI and MOLLI.

Figure 3: Repeatability of MOLLI (blue) and Open-MOLLI (red), over 14 healthy subjects: (A) Correlation with Pearson correlation coefficient squared (r^2); (B) Bland-Altman analysis for T1 values comparing between scan repetitions. Repeatability coefficients (RC) for MOLLI and Open-MOLLI are presented. Results show that repeatability is similar between MOLLI and Open-MOLLI at 3.0T.

Table 1: Acquisition parameters for in vivo acquisitions with MOLLI and Open-MOLLI sequences.

	MOLLI	Open-MOLLI
FOV (mm ²)	354×302	354×327
TR/TE (ms)	2.24/1.12	3.04/1.52
Slice Thickness (mm)	8	
FA (°)	35	
Matrix	256×144	
Reconstructed Matrix	265×218	
BW (Hz/pixel)	1085	808
Partial Fourier (%)	86	-
Minimum TI (ms)	100	171